

Estimating the Flexibility Requirements and Cost to Manage the Massive Integration of Renewables in Chile

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Abstract—This paper describes the methodology, computational tools and results of a study sponsored by the Chilean Generators’ Association (AGC) to quantify the investment and direct/indirect costs of providing the flexibility services (probabilistic dynamic reserve, modulation etc.) required for the efficient and secure operation of the Chilean power system under the projected massive variable renewable energy (VRE) insertion in the next decade.

Index Terms—Flexibility service, Operational reserve, Optimization, Power systems, Variable energy resources.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chile’s variable renewable energy (VRE) resources are among the world’s competitive: the Atacama Desert has ideal insolation characteristics, whereas wind production tends to be higher in the nighttime, thus complementing the daily solar profile. Therefore, solar and wind won most of the contract auctions in the past years and should dominate the expansion of the electrical power system of the country. This massive VRE insertion motivated government and agents to assess the *flexible generation reserve* required to manage the production from VRE: amount, type (e.g. existing hydro and thermal, new fast gas generation, pumped storage, batteries etc.) and cost (investment cost of new capacity, additional operating and maintenance (O&M) costs due to increased cycling, missed energy sales of generation allocated to reserve etc.).

This paper describes the methodology, computational aspects and results of a study sponsored by the Chilean Generators’ Association (AGC) to assess the flexibility services and costs required to manage the VRE capacity that will be built in the next decade. The study has the following steps: (i) project the capacity expansion for nine “futures” of load growth and VRE cost reduction, using a stochastic generation-transmission planning model; (ii) for each expansion of step (i), estimate the *flexibility requirements* to manage the variability of VRE production, based on a dynamic probabilistic reserve (DPR) methodology; (iii) determine the portfolio of new equipment (fast response generators, pumped storage, batteries etc.) and

existing plants (e.g. hydro and gas-fired plants) that meets the flexibility requirements of step (ii) using a stochastic co-optimization (generation and reserves) model; and (iv) estimate the *flexibility services cost* (investment, additional O&M costs) based on detailed probabilistic hourly simulations of system operation.

A. Related Work

Flexibility is defined in this paper as the capability of a system to deal with unexpected changes in generation or demand while keeping a certain level of reliability at minimum cost [1],[2]. Therefore, it is an attribute of great interest when integrating a significant amount of VRE sources [3]. For example, National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)’s study in [4] identifies the costs associated with flexibility services for thermal plants, such as increase on number of start-ups/cycling of generation. In [5], the start and stop costs for hydro generators are evaluated. The study in [6] quantifies the costs for German power plants considering up to 50 % VRE insertion and concludes that direct and indirect start-up costs are higher than ramping-related costs. Another German study [7] quantifies the number of start-ups from 2010 to 2030 and show that they are affected by changes in the generation mix, in particular, retirement of nuclear plants.

As stated in [8], just increasing the reserve margin (peak demand minus the total installed capacity) is not enough to ensure system security in the case of VREs; in order to calculate the optimal mix of generators, reserve and flexibility, some short-term constraints such as upward/downward ramps, minimum up/down time and others must be considered. For example, [9] argues that the classical unit commitment (UC) tool [10] needs to be reviewed to consider the new operational challenges brought by VREs: modified UC formulation in the literature include the representation of VRE uncertainty[11], reserve capacity[12],[13], and flexibility[14],[15].

Other factors that impact the optimal expansion when VRE is inserted are transmission planning [16] and governmental policies [17]. Some approaches to incorporate flexibility to long-term capacity planning models include: the heuristic

approach proposed in [18]; [19] stated the importance of accounting for hour-to-hour chronology and mixed-integer nature of units in generation planning models. The methodology proposed in [20] and [21] is a linear programming model, including some short-term constraints to assess flexibility issues. In order to make the size of the problem computationally tractable, the authors simplify the problem by aggregating each kind of technology in a single unit with the whole capacity, thus losing the capability of representing unit-commitment constraints. The model proposed in [22] is an hourly capacity planning, considering a resolution of 8760 hours per year, including short-term constraints. The result is a large-scale deterministic Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model. Because of the problem size, the model is not able to deal with other types of uncertainty, such as hydro inflows.

The methodology presented in this paper is based on [23], where the authors propose a capacity expansion planning model with stochastic unit commitment and integrated scenarios of inflows and VRE production, using daily load profiles for each season (or month). The model is suitable for flexibility studies because it addresses VRE and inflow uncertainty; represents UC constraints with hourly resolution; and co-optimizes generation and VRE-related reserve (*dynamic probabilistic reserve* (DPR) methodology, see section II.C and [24]).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Generation Expansion

The expansion for each load growth / VRE cost reduction “future” used the two-phase planning methodology presented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1. Two-phase expansion planning methodology

The phase 1 expansion objective is to minimize investment plus expected operation costs over a set of $s = 1, \dots, S$ scenarios that represent the variability of inflows, VRE

production and load. Those scenarios are produced by the methodology proposed in [25], a multiscale Bayesian network (monthly inflows, hourly VRE and load) that captures time and spatial co-dependences. The operational decisions are divided into $t = 1, \dots, T$ stages, typically months. In turn, each stage t contains $k = 1, \dots, K$ daily profiles (for example, $K = 2$ for weekdays and weekends). Finally, each profile k is divided into hourly steps $h = 1, \dots, 24$.

Modeling of system operation includes UC and ramping limits for thermal plants; hydro system representation (water balance in cascaded reservoirs, multipurpose constraints etc.); VRE production, including curtailment; and the transmission network (linearized active power flow or regions). The power balances are carried out for each hour of the daily load profiles. For batteries and pumped hydro, is assumed a daily regulation (initial storage=final storage for over each daily profile); for conventional hydro with reservoirs, is assumed a monthly or yearly regulation: each month is represented by a weighted set of daily profiles (e.g. 22 weekdays and 8 weekends).

The first phase expansion is solved as a large-scale MILP problem. A simplified formulation of the model's objective function (the reader should see [23] for the complete formulation) is shown below.

$$\text{Min} \sum_j I_j x_j + \sum_r I_r x_r + \frac{1}{S} \sum_s p_s \sum_t \sum_k \varphi_k \sum_j c_j g_{tkhj}^s \quad (1)$$

The first two sums are related to investment decisions: $j = 1, \dots, J$ indexes dispatchable resources (hydro, thermal, storage etc.); $r = 1, \dots, R$ indexes non-dispatchable VRE resources (wind, solar etc.); and I_j, x_j, I_r, x_r represent the respective investment costs and binary investment decisions.

The third parcel represents the expected operation cost of the dispatchable resources $\{j\}$: p_s is the probability of scenario s ; φ_k is the weight of load profile k (for example, weekdays in a month have a weight of 22/30); c_j is the operation cost of plant j (the actual formulation includes unit commitment costs and nonlinear efficiency curves); and g_{tkhj}^s is the energy produced by j in scenario s , stage t , load profile k and hour h .

A simplified formulation of the power balance equation and generation constraints is shown below:

$$\sum_j g_{tkhj}^s + \sum_r g_{tkhr}^s = d_{tkh}^s \quad \forall s, t, k, h \quad (2)$$

$$g_{tkhj}^s \leq \bar{g}_j x_j \quad \forall s, t, k, h, j \quad (3)$$

$$g_{tkhr}^s \leq \bar{g}_r x_r \quad \forall s, t, k, h, r \quad (4)$$

$$g_{tkhr}^s \leq \hat{g}_{tkhr}^s \quad \forall s, t, k, h, r \quad (5)$$

Where d_{tkh}^s is the demand in scenario s , stage t , profile k and hour h . The second constraint indicates that the generation of each plant j is limited by its capacity \bar{g}_j and the investment decision x_j (the actual formulation includes UC and minimum generation). The last two constraints indicate that VRE production depends on capacity \bar{g}_r , investment decision x_r and production scenario \hat{g}_{tkhr}^s .

In addition to the expansion plan x^* , the model solution produces a *lower bound* $E[\tilde{O}(x^*)]$ to the expected operation cost (the lower bound results from the fact that VRE production, inflows and loads for each scenario s are known values). As indicated in the Figure 1., phase 2 produces the “true” expected operation cost $E[O(x^*)]$ by carrying out a multistage stochastic optimization of system operation, with hourly resolution, proposed in [26].

B. Co-optimization of Generation and Flexibility

As mentioned, the planning model is able to co-optimize generation and flexibility-related reserve (DPR methodology). However, a requirement of the Chilean study is that the flexibility requirements should only be considered after the generation plan produced in the previous section (i.e. without co-optimization) is obtained. The reason is that the first step emulates the current Chilean market design, which does not consider co-optimization.

The flexibility requirements are then obtained by re-running the planning model, incorporating the generation investments defined in step one, and adding the DPR flexibility requirements. The model illustrated in the Figure 2. then determines the least-cost combination of new capacity (e.g. pumped storage and batteries) and assignment of existing plants to the reserve (e.g. hydro and fast-response gas).

Figure 2. Co-optimization of capacity expansion and DPR

C. Dynamic Probabilistic Reserve (DPR)

The DPR is calculated as follows:

- i. Calculate the total VRE production g_{tkh}^s for each stage, profile and hour:

$$g_{tkh}^s = \sum_r \hat{g}_{tkhr}^s x_r \quad (6)$$

Note that this total production is a variable, because it depends on the investment decisions $\{x_r\}$.

- ii. Calculate the *forecasted value* of the total production, \tilde{g}_{tkh} , over all scenarios (p_s is the forecast weight of scenario s):

$$\tilde{g}_{tkh} = \frac{1}{S} \sum_s p_s g_{tkh}^s \quad (7)$$

- iii. Calculate the *deviation* between the actual production g_{tkh}^s and forecast \tilde{g}_{tkh} :

$$\delta_{tkh}^s = g_{tkh}^s - \tilde{g}_{tkh} \quad (8)$$

- iv. Calculate the *VRE variation* Δ_{tkh}^s as the difference between deviations in two consecutive hours:

$$\Delta_{tkh}^s = \delta_{tkh}^s - \delta_{tk,h-1}^s \quad (9)$$

The values $\{\Delta_{tkh}^s, s = 1, \dots, S\}$ can be seen as *samples* of a random variable Δ_{tkh} , the VRE production variation between hours. Therefore, Δ_{tkh} is the probability distribution of flexible generation requirements.

- v. The *dynamic probabilistic reserve* \mathcal{R}_{tkh} is calculated as the convex combination of the expected value and CVaR of Δ_{tkh} :

$$\mathcal{R}_{tkh} = \lambda E(\Delta_{tkh}) + (1 - \lambda) CVaR_\alpha(\Delta_{tkh}) \quad (10)$$

The DPR formulation has two interesting features: (i) As seen, the DPR depends on linear operations over the total VRE production g_{tkh}^s , which in turn depends on the investment decisions x . In other words, the DPR requirement adjusts “automatically” to the VRE capacity in a candidate expansion plan; (ii) Because the DPR is based on a CVaR measure over the VRE scenarios, it can be incorporated to the optimal generation expansion model as a set of additional linear programming constraints.

Therefore, it becomes possible to extend the previous MIP model to *co-optimize* flexibility-related reserve and generation capacity.

The co-optimization allows a better assessment of the “portfolio” benefits of having VREs in different sites. For example, suppose that wind in site A has an average capacity factor (CF) of 40 % whereas the CF in site B is 38 %. At first sight, it would be more economical to concentrate investments in site A. However, when the DPR requirements are considered, and assuming that the spatial correlation between sites A and B is lower, the total generation plus reserve cost may be smaller if the investments are divided between A and B. In the Chile study, this effect was called “locational portfolio pricing”, in analogy with LMPs.

D. Flexibility Costs

In the third step, the flexibility costs are calculated as the sum of investment and operation costs of new reserve capacity (minus the spot revenues of the equipment when it was used in

the energy market), plus the following costs of *flexibility services* provided by the generators:

- *Start-up direct cost* $\{C_D\}$: Depends on the number of start-ups, amount of fuel to start a thermal plant, emissions and the auxiliary services necessary to start and stop the unit.

$$C_D = (C_{start} + C_{Emission})P_{max} \quad (11)$$

Where: C_{start} is the cost associated with the amount of fuel used in each start-up per MW; $C_{Emission}$ is the cost associated with the amount of CO₂ emitted in each start-up per MW; and P_{max} is the installed capacity

- *Start-up indirect cost* $\{C_I\}$: computes the costs related to an increase in inspections and maintenance periods due to an increase in cycling of generating units. It is a function of the maintenance cost, the number of startups and previous temperature states of the unit.

$$C_I = C\&M \cdot P_{max} \quad (12)$$

Where: C&M is the CAPEX and additional maintenance due to start-up per MW

- *Ramping cost* $\{C_S\}$: costs related to generators intended to operate as base loaded, but which must operate under a load tracking condition due to VRE production variability. Ramping costs are computed on when ramps exceed 20 % of capacity between consecutive hours.

$$C_S = C_{ramp} \cdot P_{max} \quad (13)$$

Where: C_{ramp} is the ramping costs per MW which vary with the type of fuel of the unit (e.g. gas-fired, coal etc.)

- *Low-efficiency cost* $\{C_E\}$: incurred by the units that, by providing reserve to the system, are required to operate at points of lower efficiency than the nominal.

$$C_E = (CE(G) - CE(G + R)) \cdot G \cdot FC \quad (14)$$

Where: $CE()$ is the specific consumption (function of generation); G is the generation; R is the reserve assignment; and FC is the fuel cost.

- *Opportunity cost* $\{C_O\}$: refers to the fact that a unit, to provide reserve to the system, must operate at lower levels of generation. Therefore, the unit incurs an opportunity cost of the energy that could have been generated in the event of a dispatch without considering reserves or as a base unit.

$$C_O = (G + R)(CM_g - CV(G + R)) - G(CM_g - CV(G)) \quad (15)$$

Where: $CV()$ is the variable cost (function of the generation) and CM_g is the load marginal cost of the connected bus

III. STUDY OVERVIEW – INPUT DATA

A. Existing System (2017)

The installed capacity of the Chilean power system in 2017 was 22 GW, for a peak demand of 10 GW. Fossil-fueled plants represent 54 % of total installed capacity (21 % coal, 20 %

diesel, 13 % gas), followed by hydro (31 %), VRE (8 % of solar and 6 % of wind) and 2 % of other technology types.

B. Load Growth & Equipment Cost Reduction “Futures”

The study horizon is 2017 to 2030 (14 years). The nine “futures” resulted from the combination of three yearly load growth (3.8 %, 2.9 % and 2 %) and three investment cost reduction scenarios (shown in Figure 3. for wind and solar).

Figure 3. Investment cost scenarios.

C. Generation Expansion Candidates

Candidates include thermal plants (gas-fired, diesel and coal), hydro, VRE (wind and solar) and storage (batteries and pumped). The VRE candidates are created with basis on the projects that participated in past power supply auctions in Chile. The total VRE candidate capacities are 19.3 GW of solar, mostly located in the country’s North region and 15.4 GW of wind, mostly in the Center and South regions.

As mentioned, the expansion planning model can capture the “portfolio effect” of low spatial correlations among inflows and wind, as well as the day complementarity of wind and solar production, illustrated in the Figure 4. for two actual plants.

Figure 4. Complementarity between solar and wind

IV. STUDY OVERVIEW - RESULTS

This section presents the main results obtained in the study for the “future” of medium load growth and medium reduction of investment costs scenarios.

A. Generation & Interconnection Expansion Model

The capacity planning model has 300 thermal plants (100 projects), 100 hydro plants, 650 wind and solar plants (500 projects) and 54 scenarios of water inflow and VRE production. Because of the long distances between VRE sites and the main load center (Santiago), the planning model also includes investments in regional interconnection reinforcements. The regional transmission system is represented by 6 buses in the Figure 5., corresponding to the likely regions for VRE deployment and known potential bottlenecks. The values correspond to the existing and future (tagged with the year where the expansion takes place on the right) transfer capacities between the 6 regions in GW. Note that Chile's transmission system is longitudinal.

Figure 5. Simplified network used in the generation expansion

As mentioned, the interconnected system operation is represented for each scenario, month, daily load profile (weekdays and weekends) with hourly resolution, including unit commitment, ramping constraints, hydro system operation and transmission limits. The phase 1 yearly MIP problem has 5.6 million constraints and 7.8 million decisions variables (3 million binary). The solution time is 4 hours in a computer with 36 processors, using the Xpress solver.

As seen in the methodology, the expansion plan found in phase 1 is simulated with a SDDP-based stochastic system operation with hourly resolution. The difference between the “true” operation cost $E[O(x^*)]$ from the stochastic operation model and the approximate (lower bound) operating cost $E[\tilde{O}(x^*)]$ produced by the planning model is used to verify the expansion's optimality, similar to the convergence criterion of Benders decomposition:

$$\frac{E[O(x^*)] - E[\tilde{O}(x^*)]}{I(x^*) + E[O(x^*)]} \leq \varepsilon \quad (16)$$

In this case (as in the other eight futures), ε is about 1.5 %, confirming the expansion's optimality.

B. Generation & Interconnection Expansion Results

The Figure 6. shows the capacity additions in each year of the study horizon (there is no addition between 2017 and 2021 because of new generation capacity already contracted in auctions). Despite a wide range of candidate generation technologies, the expansion is 100 % solar and wind.

Figure 6. VRE capacity additions per year.

Because of this massive VRE insertion, the country's generation mix changes significantly. The Figure 7. shows the expected generation by technology (average hydrological condition) for the years 2021, 2025 and 2030. The renewable component (including hydro) reaches 75 % of the energy produced in 2030. It is interesting to observe that this 75 % renewable share was the country's official target for 2050.

Figure 7. Supply mix by technology.

The Figure 8. shows a daily net load curve, i.e. demand minus VRE generation, for the years 2021, 2025 and 2030. It is notable that the final shape is very similar to the so-called “duck curve” in the US and Europe. This means that the dispatchable resources operation has become more “stressed”, with higher cycling and ramping.

Figure 8. Net load (Load – VRE generation).

The “duck curve” also confirms the concern mentioned in the Introduction about the need to install additional flexibility resources to handle the VRE variability. This is the objective of the second planning study, discussed next.

C. Reserve Requirements and Additional Expansion

The operating reserve requirement is determined for each scenario considering the methodological criteria explained in section II.B, which combines the reserve associated with the failure of conventional generation equipment with the reserve associated with the variability of VRE sources. The Figure 9. illustrates the reserve requirement related to the VRE in each year obtained after the generation expansion, which follows the increase in the VRE penetration.

Figure 9. Reserve requirement associated with variability of VRE sources.

Applying the methodology described in section II.B, the optimal reserve equipment is exclusively open cycle thermal plants as shown in the Figure 10. (the other candidates are gas-fired combined cycle and two types of battery, with storage of 3 and 14 hours).

Figure 10. Additional expansion to manage flexibility requirements

D. Hourly Simulation

After determining the flexibility requirements, detailed hourly simulations of the system operation are carried out in order to estimate the *flexibility cost components* of section II.D. In addition to unit commitment, ramping, water travel time and other operational aspects, the hourly simulations represent the same HV transmission network used by the country's System Operator in their studies; for 2017, the network had 308 buses and 460 circuits (linear active power flow model).

The Figure 11. shows the hourly short-run marginal costs (spot prices) along a month for selected years (for each month, average over the inflow/VRE scenarios; and then average over all months). Note the higher spot price variability as the VRE share increases along the years.

Figure 11. Hourly load marginal costs (average in a month).

As seen, one of the flexibility cost components is related to the increase in the start-up/shutdown cycles of the thermal units. The Figure 12. shows the evolution of the average number of start-ups is shown below for combined cycle, coal and peakers (diesel and fuel oil) thermal plants. The higher cycling of those plants is consistent with the increase in VRE penetration along the years.

Figure 12. Average number of start-ups.

E. Flexibility Costs

The Figure 13. presents a breakdown of the flexibility service costs of section II.D calculated in the hourly simulations. Note that the most relevant components are the direct and indirect start-up costs (due to the cycling rate increase). For 2030, the estimated flexibility cost is US\$ 250 million. Dividing this amount by the total VRE generation illustrated in Figure 7. , results in a flexibility service cost of 5.7 US\$/MWh.

Figure 13. Flexibility costs.

V. CONCLUSION

This work describes the methodology and computational tools used to assess the amount and costs of the flexibility resources required to handle the massive VRE insertion in Chile until 2030. The flexibility requirements are assessed by a dynamic probabilistic reserve (DPR) methodology which has two attractive features: (i) the DPR requirement adjusts “automatically” to the VRE capacity in a candidate expansion plan; and (ii) Because the DPR is based on a CVaR measure over the VRE scenarios, it can be incorporated to the optimal generation expansion model as a set of additional linear programming constraints, thus allowing the co-optimization of generation and flexibility resources.

The main insights from the Chilean system study are: (a) the expansion from 2022 until 2030 would be 95 % based on solar and wind; (b) the flexibility services would be provided by a combination of fast thermal plants and increased cycling and ramping of existing hydro and thermal plants; and (c) the cost of the flexibility services identified in (b) would be 5.7 US\$/MWh of VRE production.

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